

**PROBLÈME LEXICOLOGIQUE ET DE SÉMANTIQUE :
DIFFICULTÉS DE TRANSPOSITION DE LA TRADUCTION
ET DE L'INTERPRÉTATION DU LEXIQUE ÉWÉ
EN LANGUES ÉTRANGÈRES POUR LA TRANSMISSION
DES RÉSULTATS DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE /
LEXICOLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC ISSUES:
DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATING AND INTERPRETING
THE EWE LEXICON INTO FOREIGN LANGUAGES
FOR THE TRANSMISSION OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH FINDINGS**

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Our study focuses on the translation and interpretation of items from the Ewe language, a language of Togo, from the Niger-Congo family and the Kwa sub-branch. This study aims to demonstrate the difficulties that the researcher has in translating and interpreting research results in the major languages used for scientific dissemination, with the goal of reaching a wider audience and gaining recognition for the research undertaken. In the particular case of Togolese linguists, the trend favours publications in two languages with weight on the international scene, if it concerns scientific dissemination. These languages are English and French. However, it turns out that the translation and interpretation of Ewe in these languages, especially in French,

the language on which we will base ourselves more, is very difficult and complicated. To carry out this research, we propose to conduct it with the theory of 20th century structuralism, and especially on Ducrot's (1968) thesis, which stipulates that structure is based on the language system and represents any regular organization of linguistic structures. Ducrot further clarifies that once linguistic structures become objects of study, the issue addressed by this research is linked to the application of the principle of independence between structure and semantics. This highlights the difficulties involved in transmitting an identical semantic idea through structurally different sentences.